

Comparison and evaluation of solar photovoltaic thermal system with hybrid collector: an experimental study

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Abstract

In this paper, evaluation and comparison of a new designed PV/T hybrid collector with three PV/T systems and conventional PV in term of electrical and thermal performance is presented. The problem statement that drives this study is the nonhomogeneous distribution of heat on the PV module and in the collector, which produces a hot spot and reduce system efficiency. The proposed hybrid (oscillatory/direct flow), Web, direct and oscillatory PV/T collectors were designed and installed with a conventional PV in Oman. The outdoor experimental investigation was conducted at a mass flow rate of 0.020 kg/s. The proposed system improved the voltage and generated power by 28.5%, and 19.4%, respectively. Also, it was found that the hybrid PV/T has 9.11%, 9.98%, and 15.28% higher efficiency than oscillatory, direct and web PV/T's, respectively. From the other hand, the highest thermal efficiency was found to be 60.7% approached by the hybrid system while the highest is 53.3%, 37.0% and 18.7% for the oscillatory, direct and web collectors, respectively. Evaluation and comparison with literature result confirm that the proposed hybrid system provides a significant improvement and suitable for Oman and nearby countries with similar weather conditions.

Keywords: Photovoltaic/thermal, collector, electrical efficiency, thermal efficiency, experimental study.

1. Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) have the capacity to directly convert the solar energy into electricity. These devices are affected by the increase in their temperature resulting from trapped heat due to low conversion efficiency. To manage the temperature of the PV it is important to use cooling processes, or as an alternative hybrid Photovoltaic/Thermal (PV/T) system has to be set up [1]. To regulate the heating and cooling process, solar thermal collectors had been set up behind the PV module which are responsible for absorbing the extra heat to maintain the temperature; thus producing electricity and heat simultaneously [2]. Even till the present context scientists interested in PV/T technology have proposed and designed different system types and evaluation techniques to assess the performance and efficiency of PV/T systems [3][4].

Lv *et al.* [5], used a solar simulator examine the performance of PV/T through a thorough analysis. The observations show that there were some variations in overall output of the PV, which were basically caused by the consistent variation in the temperature of the PV, and these particular changes formed the preliminary input to a MATLAB code. Figure 1 illustrates a PV/T system which is supported with a heat exchanger and a storage tank that is well insulated [6].

Figure 1. Heat exchanger and a Storage Tank within a PV/T System [6].

The cooling methods found in the literature can be classified into active and passive cooling techniques. The later techniques are carried out by using heat sinks attached to the PV module, or latent heat storage material such as phase change material [7][8][9]. Rajput and Yang [10] designed and built a cylindrical pin fin and attached it to the back of a PV module, using a ARTIC SILVER adhesive, and compared its performance to (i) a water-cooled PV, (ii) a single-pass air collector and (iii) a bare PV module under various testing conditions. The PV modules were subjected to an irradiance of 1378.4 W/m^2 (from a halogen light). The temperature of the PV modules, observed for 150 minutes, was measured, and the highest temperature after 150 minutes was observed for the bare PV module with $88.81 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The

best cooling was achieved by the single-channel PV/T and followed by PV/T cooled with the heat sink which exhibited a temperature of 58.45 °C. Elbreki et al. [11] used Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) to view the behaviour of PV module cooled with lapping fins heat sink and integrated with a planar reflector, to concentrate the incident sunlight, and the system was tested in an outdoor environment. From the experiments, the authors found the bare PV module temperature to peak at 65 °C while the PV cooled with lapping fins to peak at 40 °C.

Aste *et al.* [12] led an experiment on a water-based flat plate PV/T system. From the research it was noticed that the air gaps existence and non-existence, which is created from the crystalline outer covering, configuration of the absorber, as well as the PV system that is adopted, all have a crucial role to play in determining the efficiency. The study results indicated that the electrical efficiencies achieved were 6% and 14.2% for the covered and uncovered systems, respectively. The total efficiencies for the covered and uncovered systems were relatively similar as they achieved 35% and 36%, respectively.

Zhou *et al.* [13] conducted an indoor and outdoor research on the PV/T cogeneration system, where totally thirty-six PV/T collectors are brought in use and each single row has six collectors attached to each other in a sequence. Finally, when six collectors were connected in series and six in parallel, the electrical and thermal efficiencies achieved were calculated to be 10.9% and 41.4%, respectively. The main challenges in research for multiple PV/T systems is the balance between the optimum connection of PV systems and optimum connection of solar thermal systems.

He *et al.* [14] conducted an extensive research where both flat plate solar thermal as well as flat plate PV/T collector were used. Apart from this the superficial glass shield covering often used above the collectors was the main purpose of the research. Through the experiment it was noticed that the average day-to-day electrical performance of the PV modules was 6.5%, when the outer glass covering was not brought in used. But, at the same time the thermal performance of the system reduced, and its efficiency was measured to be 26.4%.

Jin *et al.* [15] utilized the single pass of PV/T to recover waste heat. The findings are consistent with the literature, where the proposed system led to a raise in electrical yield, in addition to the thermal yield. The electrical, thermal and overall efficiencies were enhanced to 10.0%, 54.7% and 64.7%, respectively, at an ambient temperature of 25°C. The cooling aspect in PV/T systems is highly affected by many parameters such as the mass flow rate and the heat transfer coefficient. The change of the flow within the PV/T collector will lead to a change in the cooling as well. In designing a pipe or channel configuration, researchers aim at avoiding designs with high pressure drops and pumping losses. Sopian *et al.* [16] conducted an experiment where three different PV/T water collectors were tested to ascertain

their efficacies in terms of thermal productivity. The study considered the parallel, direct and split flow design configuration. After a detailed investigation of their thermal yield, it was noticed that the split flow design exhibits the highest thermal efficiency at a solar irradiance of 1000 W/m² and ambient temperature of 25 °C. Although split flow exhibited a higher peak thermal efficiency, the difference did not exceed 1%.

Aside from the pipe design configuration, the retention of the heated water is also important for applications of PV/T systems. Thakare *et al.* [17] developed an analytical system to assess the optimal water replenishment profile to optimize the system configuration of PV/T's. The research was carried out to investigate the impact of water replenishment on the sizing of PV/T systems. The methodologies were demonstrated by considering the patterns of hot water usage of residential as well as industrial settings. The authors observed that for the optimized make up water profile, the profile of storage temperature remained constant. The research demonstrated significant reductions in PV/T collector area and storage volume for both residential and industrial settings.

According to an experiment tests by Kim *et al.* [18] and Hosseini *et al.* [19] on hybrid PV/T system with water collector tested to conduct the influence of wetted and sheet and tube absorbers. Finally, the results of experiment revealed that wetted absorbers could produce combined PV/T performance of 65.0%, whereas sheet and tube were able to produce 60.6% of combined PV/T performance [18]. Table 1 summarizes the aforementioned studies.

Table 1. Summary of the Literature Review

Reference	Location	Year	Type of cooler/fluid	Efficiency (%)			Environmental conditions	Test duration/date
				Electrical	Thermal	PV/T		
[20]	China	2015	Water	~10.5%	45.0%	*54.5%	Max. SR. 850 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 36°	31 March 2014
				~10.1%	50.0%	*59.3%	Max. SR. 700 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 20°C	13 May 2014
[21]	Malaysia	2013	Air - single path Air - double paths	~9.9% ~9.4%	~21.0% ~46.5%	*30.9% *55.9%	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 29.5°C	May 2012
[22]	Oman	2020	Water - spiral flow Water - direct flow Water - web flow	9.11% 8.7% 8.7%	26.0% 19.3% 9.8%	35.1% 28% 18.5%	Max. SR. 880 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 38°C Max. WS. 11 m/s	July 2019
[23]	Norway	2015	Glycol – water mixture	12.0%	71.5%	83.5%	Annual SR. 1150 kWh m ⁻² Avg. Temp. 6.3 °C	-
[24]	Malaysia	2019	Silicon Carbide - Nanofluid	13.7%	72.0%	*84%	Max. Temp. 31°C Max. WS. 10 m/s RH. 66%	May and July 2018

[25]	China	2015	Water	14.9%	48.4%	63.4%	Max. SR. 931 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 31.5°C	10, 11 and 14 May 2014
[8]	Switzerland	2013	Water	~12.5%	-	-	Max. Monthly Avg. SR. 180 kWhm ⁻²	May 2013 to April 2014
[26]	Algeria	2016	Air	~10.0%	~62.0%	*72.0%	Max. SR. 817 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 24°C	November 2014
[27]	South Korea	2015	Air	15.0%	23.0%	38.0%	Max. SR. 1050 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 0°C	December to March 2014
[18]	China	2012	Water	~15.3%	70.0%	*85.3%	-	-
[28]	Canada	2016	Air	~16.7%	~ 45.5%	*50.8%	Max air flow rate 800 kg/h Max. WS. 2 m/s	Summer and Winter 2015
[29]	Czech Republic	2014	Water	9.1%	63.0%	*72.1%	Avg. SR. 931- 1206 Wm ⁻² Avg. Temp. 17- 19 °C	-
[30]	Czech Republic	2014	Water	15%	78%	-	-	-
[12]	Italy	2017	Water	6.0%	30.0%	36.0%	-	-
[3]	UK	2015	Water - Serpentine flow Water - Header riser flow	7.4% 7.2%	57.1% 54.7%	61.7% 59.2%	Max. SR. 993 Wm ⁻² Temp. 25 °C	-
[31]	India	2015	Water	12.4%	59%	71.4%	Max. SR. 950 Wm ⁻²	April to May 2014
[32]	Malaysia	2018	Water	13.75%	81.0%	93%	Max. SR. 1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 33°C WS. 2 m/s	March 2016
[33]	China	2015	Water	30.0%	30.0%	60.0%	Max. SR. 650 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 17°C	December 2014
[34]	Malaysia	2016	Air	14.0%	56.2%	93.1%	Max. SR. 700 Wm ⁻²	-
[13]	China	2017	Water	10.9%	41.4%	*52.3%	Max. SR. 900 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 6 °C	One-month heating season
[15]	Malaysia	2010	Air	10.0%	54.7%	64.7%	Max. SR. 817.4 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 25°C	-
[35]	Iran	2015	Water	~9.2%	~54.7%	*63.9%	Max. monthly Avg. SR. 250 kWhm ⁻² Max. Temp. 31°C	January 2001 to March 2003
[14]	China	2013	Water	5.7%	34.1%	*39.8%	Avg. SR. 701.6 Wm ⁻²	9 to 11 April 2013 8 May 2013
[36]	India	2017	Air	14.6%	60.7%	83.0%	Max. SR=994 Wm ⁻² Avg. Temp. 27 °C Max. Temp. 33.4 °C RH. 86%	15 May 2017
[37]	Singapore	2012	Water – flowing in tube Water – flowing in channels	11.8% 11.5%	40.7% 39.4%	*52.5% *50.9%	Max. SR. 860 Wm ⁻²	-

							Max. Temp. 34.5°C	
[38]	UAE	2014	Water	11.5%	58.8%	70.3%	Max. SR. 899.7 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 35.8°C	April 2014
[39]	India	2016	Water	16.2%	36.1%	52.3%	Max. SR. 850 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 35°C WS. 1.3 m/s	4 June 2015 and 6 th -10 th May
[40]	Tunisia	2016	Water	15.0%	50.0%	*65.0%	Max. SR. 1070 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 42.9°C	July 2014
[41]	Greece	2007	Air	10.0%	52.0%	62.0%	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 20°C WS. 1.5 m s ⁻¹	-
[42]	Malaysia	2014	Water	11.4%	51.0%	62.0%	Max. SR. 690 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 37°C	-
[19]	Iran	2011	Water	~4.4%	-	~26.8%	Max. SR. 1060 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 26.3°C	18th of September, 2010
[43]	Italy	2016	Water	13.2%	62.0%	75.2%	Max. SR~1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 28 °C	11 days in September and 9 days in October
[16]	Malaysia	2011	Water – direct flow Water – parallel flow Water – split flow	-	~50.8% ~50.6% ~51.4%	-	Max. SR. 1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 25°C	-
[44]	Iran	2016	-Alumina-water nanofluid -Silver-water nanofluid	11.5% 11.1%	84.0% 81.0%	90.0% 92.5%	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻²	-
[45]	Malaysia	2016	Silicon Dioxide-Water nanofluid Titanium oxide-water nanofluid Silicon Carbide-Water nanofluid	10.3% 13.5% 10.9%	65.9% 68.2% 66.9%	76.2% 81.7% 77.9%	Max. SR. 1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. ~ 42°C	-
[17]	India	2016	Water	9.7%	-	-	Max. SR ~ 930 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 29°C	15 March 2015

(-) refers to not stated or not part of the study, for instance, numerical studies may not require the actual time of data or experimentation period. Moreover, indoor experiments do not require stating the date, given that the environmental conditions are controlled. In some cases, the overall PV/T efficiency is not mentioned, and hence it is calculated as the algebraic sum of electrical and thermal efficiencies reported. (Max.) denotes maximum, (Avg.) denotes average, (Temp.) denotes temperature, (SR.) denotes solar radiation, (RH.) denotes relative humidity, (WS.) denotes Wind speed, (~) denotes approximate values, used for values taken from figures and not stated in the text. (*) denotes calculated values by the authors of this paper, by algebraically adding the electrical and thermal efficiencies of the same collector and at the same time/conditions.

Based on the literature survey in table 1 the following points are worthy of being highlighted:

- It is further noticed that there are various types of cooling methods that are often used to maintain the surface temperature of the PV. Also, there are different types of PV/T collector designs that can utilize the same type of working fluid. Sopian *et al.* [21] used an air-based PV/T with single-path and double-path to view the difference in their performance, while Ibrahim *et al.* [42] used a spiral flow absorber for a water-based PV/T.

- Figure 2 shows the main collectors explored in the conducted research. However, many elements are essential to specify cooling effectivity such as collector size, shape, material used, etc. The collectors are named by their shapes as example direct means the fluid will flow directly in the pipes, Web mean the collector take the Web shape. The differences in shape will impact the flow of the heat transfer fluid and the overall heat transfer coefficient. The use of a particular absorber shape is selected based on its uniformity, pressure drop, heat transfer area, etc.
- The configuration type has been presumed to be standalone PV/T system as it has not been specified in each case. However, less research for testing the different design parameters is made with consideration for grid-connected PV/T systems.
- From Table 1 and the literature it is found that the PV/T cooled using air, water, air/water, nanofluid, phase change material (PCM), nanofluid/PCM, water jet impingement, etc. as shown in Figure 3.
- The PV/T systems shows their viability in many applications especially in building-integrated and grid-connected compared with separate thermal water heater or PV array. For instance, Ahn *et al.* [27] installed four PV/T collectors with a capacity of 1 kW at an inclination of 30 degrees on the rooftop of a building with a southern orientation. While Rounis *et al.* [28] used the building for single inlet and multiple inlets for airflow to be used for the collector.
- The collector's configurations shown in Fig. 2 illustrates the differences in the covered part attached to the back PV module. However, the uncovered part will have different temperature from the cooled cover parts. This situation will produce hotspots on the PV module and change the related cells characteristics [46][47].
- In the oscillatory and serpentine collector, it is found that the inlet water is cooled, and it gets heated and became warmer particularly in the second half of the collector. This situation makes the temperature distribution to be nonhomogeneous over the PV module and hence it is hotter in the second half of the PV module.

The last two points, which are problems, could be solved by the newly proposed hybrid oscillatory/direct type PV/T collector, where the first half is an oscillatory collector and the second half is a direct collector. The proposed system will be investigated and compared with some of the known collectors. However, it opens the door for the researchers to investigate more hybrid systems.

The present study aims to design, investigate, and evaluate four PV/T systems with different collectors (oscillatory, direct, web, hybrid oscillatory/direct) under desert weather conditions. However, the proposed hybrid oscillatory/direct was designed, evaluated, and compared with other PV/T and conventional systems. The growth of solar energy usage and applications in Oman and other Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries motivate the current research. However, the electrical (current, voltage, power, efficiency) and thermal (inlet, outlet, cell temperatures, efficiency) will be investigated in outdoor conditions. Solar irradiance and ambient temperature effect will be studied, and a comparison of PV/T systems and PV will be considered. The study will compare the investigated systems with other systems in literature based on Table 1.

Figure 2. Types of PVT collectors depending on the coolant flow method (a) Direct (b) Spiral (c) Serpentine, (d) Parallel, (e) Split, (f) Oscillatory, (g) Web

Figure 3. Classification of PV/T collectors.

2. The Study Methodology

In this study, different PV/T systems were designed, evaluated, and compared with a conventional PV to find the best solar energy option for Oman and GCC countries. However, one of the PV/T systems is proposed (hybrid collector) in this study, which opens the door for hybrid collectors to be investigated. The systems were all tested under the same weather conditions, for the city of Sohar. The electrical and thermal performances were investigated. Figure 4(a) shows research activities sequences in this study. Also, Figure 4(b) illustrates the research methodology adopted to meet the current research aims.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Research methodology flowchart (a) research activities, (b) research justifications.

3. Experimental setup

3.1 The location of study

Sohar is in the far north-east of the Sultanate of Oman overlooking the Gulf of Oman and is 234 km to the northwest of the sultanate’s capital Muscat city. Sohar city is characterized by hot weather in summer, moderate in winter, and is also characterized by a high relative humidity due to the proximity to the Gulf waters, as this rate rises in the summer, and less in the rest of the year [48][49]. The productivity and performance of a PV depends directly on the weather data of the construction area. Therefore, the recording of weather variables such as solar irradiance, ambient temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed are important factors to determine/predict the amount of electricity to be generated from the PV. However, the wind speed in June 2020 found to be in the ranged of 6-13 mph, while the humidity is in the ranged Of 45-60%. The impact of the two elements was not considered in this study because of the high impact of solar irradiance and ambient temperature on the PV/T systems compared with humidity and wind speed. Also, this situation makes the investigation consistent with other studies in literature, where humidity and wind speed are not considered.

Sohar is located between latitudes 24.35° and longitudes 56.70° E and its biomes include beaches, mountains and the desert. Kazem [50] indicated that the average solar irradiance in this country is 5.197 kW/m²/day, and the duration of the sun hours ranges between 8.0 and 10.5 hours per day. Figure 5 shows the weather data of Sohar on the 29th of June 2020.

Figure 5. Sohar weather data.

3.2 System description and materials

The studied system contains four separated PV/T modules and a conventional PV as shown in Figure 6(a). The investigated PV/Ts are (PV/T1) oscillatory, (PV/T2) direct, (PV/T3) web flow and (PV/T4) hybrid direct/oscillatory design as shown in Figure 6(b). The four PV/T systems designed and installed in Renewable Energy Lab at Sohar University, Oman. There are two storage tanks one for inlet water and one for the outlet. All four systems are connected to the mentioned tanks and water circulated through pipes. All PV modules for the PV/T systems have the same specifications of the conventional PV, which is 100 W, 5.94 A, and 22.32 V for rated power, short circuit current and open circuit voltages, respectively. The electrical loads connected to each system is 100 Ω resistance. Water flow meter sensor is connected to measure the flow rate and K-type temperature sensors are connected to each system's inlet, outlet, and cell to measure the temperature. The water pump rating is 0.5 hours' power and the voltage, current and power are measured using sensors, which are connected through Arduino to the PC as shown in Figure 6(c).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. (a) PV/T experimental setup, (b) system diagram (web, direct, oscillatory, hybrid), (c) test procedure.

3.3 System's performance calculation

Electrical performance evaluated by measuring the maximum power point current (I_m) and voltage (V_m) for different systems. However, the multiplication of I_m and V_m will produce power P_m . In addition, the electrical energy generated is calculated as follows [51][52]:

$$\eta_{electrical} = \frac{P_m}{G \times A_{module}} \quad (1)$$

where G is the solar irradiance in W/m^2 .

The collector heat calculated using as follows [51][53]:

$$Q_u = \dot{m} C_p (T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad (2)$$

where \dot{m} , C_p , T_{out} and T_{in} are the mass flow rate, heat capacity, inlet, and outlet temperatures, respectively. However, the collector heat used to calculate the PV/T thermal efficiency as follows:

$$\eta_{thermal} = \frac{Q_u}{G_u \times A_c} \quad (3)$$

By adding the electrical ($\eta_{electrical}$) and thermal ($\eta_{thermal}$) efficiencies the system overall (η_t) efficiency will be calculated.

3.4 Uncertainty Analysis

During measurements errors occurred for different reasons such as human errors, tools errors, devices errors, etc. To guarantee high quality measurements, it is essential to specify percentage errors of reading. So that, it is essential to evaluate uncertainty for the different sensor's findings (flow meter, K-type, etc.). Kline and McClintock [54] method were used for evaluating vulnerability in the conducted experiments output such as (flow rate, temperature, efficiencies, etc.) as follows:

$$W_R = \left[\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_1} w_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_2} w_2 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_n} w_n \right)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

Where, W is the uncertainties, R is the function, and x is the independents variables. Hence, the uncertainty in the experiments are provided below:

$$W_{R_1} = [(0.012)^2 + (0.18)^2 + (0.1)^2 + (0.9)^2 + (1.01)^2]^{0.5} = 1.368$$

The thermal, electrical, and overall efficiencies measurements' uncertainties, respectively, are:

$$W_{R_2} = [(1.1)^2 + (0.18)^2 + (0.20)^2]^{0.5} = 1.132$$

$$W_{R_3} = [(0.06)^2 + (0.07)^2]^{0.5} = 0.092$$

$$W_R = [(1.368)^2 + (1.132)^2 + (0.092)^2]^{0.5} = 1.801$$

With less than 2% measurement uncertainty, it is clear seen that high-precision geometrically acceptable measurements have been conducted.

4. Results and Discussions

The four PV/T systems and conventional PV were designed and installed in Sohar University, Oman. The systems were investigated in the outdoors to evaluate their electrical and thermal performances. Moreover, comparison with published research in the literature is presented in the validation section based on table 1. The mass flow rate is essential element for cooling the PV module added to the collector configuration and solar irradiance. In general, increasing mass flow rate will lead to a decrease in the PV temperature. However, for the indoor experiments optimum mass flow rate specified in relation to the solar irradiance as irradiance and ambient temperature can be kept constant while varying the mass flow rate. However, for the outdoors, with variation in the solar irradiance, it is difficult to specify the best mass flow rate. However, to neutralize the mass flow rate a 0.020 kg/s was used in this study to be consistent with some studies in literature [55][52][56][57]. It is important to note that all systems began operation in the same time, to ensure a fair comparison, moreover that none of these collectors was shaded or tilted at different angle or direction.

4.1 Electrical performance

Current and voltage of the Photovoltaic are impacted by different conditions that the PV experiences. To accurately assess the utility of different PV/T designs, it is important to record and assess the variation in the voltage, current and power of the PV module. Figure 7 shows the PV currents and voltages for the investigated systems. The current waveforms in Figure 7(a) is approximately bell shape. In another word, the current shape similar to the solar irradiance shape in Figure 5. This is because PV current is significantly affected by the solar irradiance. However, the conventional PV current is slightly higher than the PV/T systems' currents due to the temperature, which is highest in the PV. At 8 AM, the PV current is approximately 2.5 A, while the PV/T with direct flow produced a current of 2.3 A. Furthermore, the hybrid PV/T have the lowest current, overall, because of cooling with small difference from the oscillatory PV/T. At 12 PM, the PV/T with hybrid configuration exhibits the lowest current, although the difference is insignificant, it remains to prove the point that temperature positively affect output current, however, in a slight manner. This observation is similar to those found in the literature [58][59][60].

Voltage behaves differently, where cell temperature leads to its drop and it can be significant. Figure 7(b) illustrates the investigated system's voltages. Almost, all voltage shapes are having the same trend. However, the hybrid PV/T have the highest voltage ± 18 V due to the cooling compared with conventional PV, which have ± 14 V. This situation means that 28.5% improvement in voltage occurred in the hybrid system. The difference in cell temperature is noticeable at 8 AM because the systems operate prior to that time. The measured voltages at 8 AM for the PV, PV/T web flow, PV/T direct flow, PV/T oscillatory flow and PV/T hybrid flow were 13.7 V, 16.3 V, 17.1 V, 17.4 V and 17.7 V. The differences in voltage increase throughout the day and become more distinct from 10 AM to 2:30 PM. Throughout the day, the lowest voltages produced by the PV/T systems were observed for the web flow configuration, while the oscillatory design produced the second highest voltages, followed by the direct flow configuration. The discrepancy between the measured PV/T voltage and PV voltage has been observed by many research studies [61].

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Investigated systems (a) current, (b) voltage

Figure 8(a) shows the generated power for the studied systems. The first observation is that the power shape is similar to the current in Figure 7(a). There is an improvement in the power generated, which shows that the hybrid system has the highest power. The decrease in the generated current, relative to the PV current, was insignificant compared with the significant increase in the voltage. The power generated from the conventional PV was 54.1 W compared with 64.6 W generated from the hybrid PV/T in the middle of the day. This case highlight increment in the generated power up to 19.4%. As stated previously, the difference in cooling become more observable throughout the day, where at 9 AM, the power generated by the PV/T with hybrid design was 0.24% higher than that with the oscillatory design. However, at 12 PM, the power generated by the hybrid system was 1.89% higher than the power of the oscillatory design. At 9 AM, the PV power rose by 6.23%, 10.82%, 14.8% and 15% for the web, direct, oscillatory and hybrid design, respectively. While at 12 PM, the PV power rose by 7.39%, 15.15%, 16.82% and 19.03%, respectively.

The PV electrical efficiencies for the tested systems are shown in Figure 8(b). The results are as expected based on the generated power that the hybrid system has the highest efficiency 12.7% compared with 10.4% for the conventional PV. However, the oscillatory system coming second, then direct and finally web collector. The electrical efficiencies illustrated if Figure 8(c) in term of $(T_i - T_a)/G$ to clarify the trend. The relational expression for electrical efficacies found to be $\eta_{hybrid} = 0.0004\Delta T/G + 0.0958$, $\eta_{oscillatory} = 0.0004\Delta T/G + 0.0878$, $\eta_{direct} = 0.000004\Delta T/G + 0.0871$ and $\eta_{web} = 0.0004\Delta T/G + 0.0831$. At zero reduced temperature, the efficiency is 0.0958, 0.0878, 0.0871 and 0.0831, respectively, and the electricity loss coefficient is 0.0004, 0.0004, 0.000004 and 0.0004, respectively. From the trend results and the discussed relational expression, it is found that hybrid PV/T has 9.11%, 9.98%, and 15.28% higher efficiency than oscillatory, direct and web, respectively. The efficiency difference appears to be significant and approximately, 0.80%, 0.87%, and 1.27% with respect to oscillatory, direct and web, respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. Investigated system: (a) power, (b) electrical efficiency, (c) efficiency in term of $(T_i - T_a)/G$.

4.2 Thermal performance

To evaluate the thermal performance of the investigated PV/T systems and compare them with ambient temperature and solar irradiance, measurements has been taken and illustrated in Figure 9(a). The PV cell temperatures of the tested systems follow the solar irradiance shape. However, the conventional PV cell have the highest temperature and the hybrid system have the lower temperatures. The temperatures range is approximately 40.26 - 65.85 °C, 37.45 – 62.69 °C, 35.93 – 58.42 °C, 35.26 – 49.31 °C, and 33.98 – 45.21 °C, respectively. Using the proposed hybrid PV/T system reduced the temperature by around 20 °C. The collected heat from the PV/T systems could be used for many applications such as ventilation, building heating, air drying, etc.

Figure 9(b) shows the water temperatures used for cooling the PV/T systems. It is found that the proposed hybrid system absorbs more thermal energy. However, Web PV/T system performs the least in absorbing heat from the solar cells. Furthermore, the proposed hybrid system shows that the solar cell temperature is almost flatten and approximately homogenous through the day and particularly in the middle of the day. This is a credit for this system and prevent the solar cell from getting hotspots.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. PV/T systems (a) cell temperatures, (b) outlet water temperature.

Figure 10(a) and (b) shows a comparison of the thermal and overall efficiencies for the investigated PV/T systems. The highest thermal efficiency was 60.7% approached by the hybrid system while the peak thermal efficiencies are 53.3%, 37.0% and 18.7% for the oscillatory, direct and Web collectors, respectively. However, the PV/T systems overall efficiency shown in Figure 10(b), which is calculated by adding electrical to thermal efficiencies, found that the hybrid system has the highest efficiency with 68.6% compared with 60.8% for the oscillatory collector. This means that the hybrid system improves the overall system efficiency by 12.8%.

(b)

Figure 10. Investigated PV/T (a) thermal efficiencies, (b) overall system efficiencies.

4.3 Comparison and validation

To compare and validate the achieved results, a stack bar chart is used for both electrical and thermal efficiencies for the studied system and other systems in literature of table 1. Figure 11(a) shows that the investigated PV/T systems efficiencies are consistent with other systems. However, the thermal efficiency is higher compared with electrical efficiency and this is a trend in PV/T systems. The thermal efficiency affected by many parameters such as the absorber type, fluid used, mass flow rate, weather data, cooling method, etc as illustrated in table 2. Also, it is observed that some systems' exhibit peak overall efficiencies which are higher than 80% such as [24] and [45]. These mentioned systems used nanofluid to absorb more heat and improve overall system efficiency. Also, the overall system efficiencies as shown in Figure 11(b) for the studied PV/T found to be 68.61%, 60.86%, 44.11% and 25.07% for proposed hybrid, oscillatory, direct and Web PV/T's, respectively.

The PV/T systems overall efficiencies are difficult to be used for comparison, but it gives an indication about the system usage and ability to collect solar energy. Some researchers calculated the highest overall PV/T efficiency by adding the highest electrical and thermal efficiencies throughout the day even if they reach in different time, which is not correct. However, the PV/T overall efficiency found to have different range based on the cooling method. The range between 70s-80s% mainly achieved by using nanoparticles in nanofluid, nano/PCM and hybrid nanofluid-nano/PCM as Tables 1 and 2 depicts. However, systems which used water only for cooling has efficiency ranged from 20% to 70%, as the results of Table 2 indicate. With 68.61% efficiency, the proposed hybrid collector shows that it is in the higher range of its category. The use of nanofluids is an expensive process, as it requires mixing the nanoparticles with the basic fluid and then re-mixing them at specific intervals to ensure the continuation of its high thermal conductivity. Also, the use of phase change materials (PCM) with addition of nanoparticles to increase their thermal

conductivity is an additional cost. Here, the cost-benefit (efficiency) must be settled. In such a case, the proposed hybrid system can be considered excellent and practical as well.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11. PV/T efficiencies (a) electrical and thermal, (b) overall.

Table 2. The design and operation conditions of the compared systems in Fig. 11

Reference	Working fluid	Thermal component	Electrical component	Environmental conditions
Li et al. [34]	Water	Static miniature solar concentrator Flat plate	Crystalline PV – Building integrated	Max. SR. 700 Wm ⁻² Avg. Temp. 16.9 °C Max. SR. 850 Wm ⁻² Avg. Temp. 32.7 °C
Sopian et al. [36]	Air	Flat plate air base Single-path and Double-paths	Bifacial Photovoltaic	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 29.5 °C
Kazem et al. [37]	Water	Web-type, Direct-type, Spiral-type	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 880 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 38 °C Max. WS. 11 m/s
Good et al. [38]	Water	Flat plate	Mono- and Polycrystalline PV	One-year data imported from Meteonorm
Al-Waeli et al. [39]	Silicon Carbide -Water nanofluid	Flat plate	Polycrystalline PV	Max. Temp. 31 °C Max. WS. 10 m/s RH. 66%
Zhang et al. [40]	Water	Flat heat pipe	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 931 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 31 °C
Rommel et al. [14]	Water	Flat plate	Crystalline PV	Max. Monthly Avg. SR. 180 kWhm ⁻²
Tabet et al. [41]	Air	Metallic plates with fins	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 817 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 24 °C
Ahn et al. [42]	Air	Baffle flat plate	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 1050 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 0 °C
Kim and Kim [18]	Water	Sheet-and-tube type and the fully wetted type	Monocrystalline PV	-
Rounis et al. [43]	Air	Single and Multiple-inlet air channel – building integrated	-	Max air flow rate 800 kg/h Max. WS. 2 m/s
Pokorny et al. [24]	Water	Copper absorber – Sheet-and-tube	Monocrystalline PV	Avg. SR. 931-1206 Wm ⁻² Avg. Temp. 17-19 °C
Aste et al. [19]	Water	Two roll-bond aluminium absorbers with channels arrangement	Microcrystalline	-
Allan et al. [7]	Water	Water Serpentine-flow Water Header riser-flow	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 993 Wm ⁻² Temp. 25 °C
Palaskar and Deshmukh [44]	Water	Spiral-flow heat exchanger	PV with flat reflectors	Max. SR. 950 Wm ⁻²
Jaaz et al. [16]	Water	Jet impingement cooler	Polycrystalline PV with a Compound Parabolic Concentrator	Max. SR. 1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 33 °C WS. 2 m/s
Xu et al. [20]	Water	Grooved tube	PV with Fresnel lens (concentrating ratio of 1090x)	Max. SR. 650 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 17 °C
Mojumder et al. [46]	Air	Flat plate with cooling fins	Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR. 700 Wm ⁻²
Zhou et al. [21]	Water	Parallel copper pipes	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 900 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 6 °C
Jen et al. [27]	Air	Single pass rectangle tunnel with tunnel bars	Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR. 817 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 25 °C
Jahromi et al. [47]	Water	Flat plate	Monocrystalline PV	Max. Monthly Avg. SR. 250 kWm ⁻² Max. Temp. 31 °C
He and Xiao [22]	Water	Flat plate	-	-
Das et al. [17]	Air	Single pass Flat plate	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 994 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 33.4 °C RH. 86%
Dubey and Tay [23]	Water	- Tube-and-sheet, and - Parallel-plate channels	Monocrystalline PV Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR. 860 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 34.5 °C

Alzaabi et al. [48]	Water	Rectangular copper pipes configured as a Parallel-tube Flat plate collector		Max. SR. 899.7 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 35.8°C
Hazami et al [49]	Water	Flat plate	Monocrystalline PV	Max. SR. 1070 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 42.9°C
Tonui and Tripanagnostopoulo [50]	Air	Single pass air channel with fins Double pass air channel	Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 20°C WS. 1.5 m s ⁻¹
Ibrahim rt al. [51]	Water	Spiral-flow square absorber	Polycrystalline PV – Building integrated	Max. SR. 690 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 37°C
Rosa-Clot et al. [52]	Water	Polycarbonate box (PC) with partition vectors	Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR~1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 28 °C
Khanjari et al [53]	Alumina-water nanofluid and Silver-water nanofluid	Sheet-and-tube, direct-flow, collector	-	Max. SR. 800 Wm ⁻²
Al-Shamani et al. [55]	Silicon dioxide-Water nanofluid, Titanium oxide-water nanofluid, Silicon Carbide-Water nanofluid	Rectangular tube absorber	Polycrystalline PV	Max. SR. 1000 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. ~42°C
Thakare et al. [31]	Water	Flat plate	-	Max. SR. 930 Wm ⁻² Max. Temp. 30°C
This study (Hybrid)	Water	Hybrid (oscillatory/direct) flow flat plate	Polycrystalline	Max. SR. 880 W/m ² Max. temp. 35°C RH. 45-60%
This study (Oscillatory)	Water	Oscillatory-flow flat plate	Polycrystalline	Max. SR. 880 W/m ² Max. temp. 35°C RH. 45-60%
This study (Direct)	Water	Direct-flow flat plate	Polycrystalline	Max. SR. 880 W/m ² Max. temp. 35°C RH. 45-60%
This study (Web)	Water	Web-flow flat plate	Polycrystalline	Max. SR. 880 W/m ² Max. temp. 35°C RH. 45-60%
Single-crystalline PV's are referred to as Monocrystalline PV's, and Multi-crystalline PV's are referred to as polycrystalline in this table. (-) refers to not stated or not part of the study, for instance, the type of the PV is not mentioned or not clarified. (Max.) denotes maximum, (Avg.) denotes average, (Temp.) denotes temperature, (SR.) denotes solar radiation, (RH.) denotes relative humidity, (WS.) denotes Wind speed.				

5. Conclusions

In this paper, a PV/T with hybrid collector (oscillatory/direct) was proposed, designed, evaluated, and compared with conventional PV and three PV/T systems (Web, direct, oscillatory). The aim is to make the temperature distribution on the PV module uniform or homogenous. The experiments and investigation were conducted in Sohar, Oman. The electrical and thermal performance was measured and discussed for each PV/T. A 0.020 kg/s mass flow rate was used. It is found that the highest voltage and power achieved was by the proposed hybrid system which are ±18 V and 64.6 W compared with ±14 V and 54.1 W of the conventional PV, respectively. In all experiments the hybrid system shows the highest values in term of voltage, power and efficiency. The electrical, and thermal system efficiencies for the proposed model are 12.7%, and 60.7% compared with 11.94% and 53.3%, 11.13% and 37.0% and 11.16% and 18.7% for the oscillatory, direct and Web collectors, respectively. It is found that hybrid PV/T has 9.11%, 9.98%, and 15.28% higher efficiency than oscillatory, direct and web,

respectively. The efficiency difference appears to be significant and approximately, 0.80%, 0.87%, and 1.27% with respect to oscillatory, direct and web, respectively. The temperatures range is approximately 40.26 - 65.85 °C, 37.45 – 62.69 °C, 35.93 – 58.42 °C, 35.26 – 49.31 °C, and 33.98 – 45.21 °C for hybrid, oscillatory, direct and web, respectively. Using the proposed hybrid PV/T system reduced the temperature by around 20 °C compared with conventional PV. It is found that the investigated PV/T systems efficiencies are consistent with other systems. However, the thermal efficiency is higher compared with electrical efficiency and this is a trend in PV/T systems. The thermal efficiency affected by many parameters such as the absorber type, fluid used, mass flow rate, weather data, cooling method, etc. However, the proposed system approved its productivity in Oman weather and countries with similar weather conditions. Also, use of nanoparticles to improve the working fluid is expected to lead to a high thermal conduction, efficiencies and power production. We recommend for future work to conduct indoor investigation to get more information about system behaviours in term of optimal conditions by looking into the system parameters separately such as solar irradiance, temperature, mass flow rate, etc.

Declaration of interest statement

“We the authors declare no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript”.

Conflict of Interests

“The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper”.

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